

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

MANAGEMENT OF INFORMATION SYSTEM DIGITALIZATION IN UNIVERSITY SUBDIVISIONS

Sava L.,

*Associate Professor, PhD,
Technical University of Moldova,
ORCID: 0000-0002-4318-9486*

Tirsu V.

*Associate Professor, PhD,
Technical University of Moldova
ORCID: 0000-0002-1726-792X*

Abstract

Considering the rapid evolution of digitalization at the national level, digital transformation has become essential for enhancing academic and administrative activities. The study underscores the importance of digitalizing documents and management processes through the implementation of the Electronic Individual Plan and the Electronic Report for tracking educational, methodological, and scientific activities. Using MS Excel applications, the developed solutions ensure a unified, accessible, and efficient platform for all university subdivisions. Digitalization brings numerous benefits, including time and resource savings, simplification of administrative procedures, increased transparency, and enhanced real-time information access. The digital transformation of the university information system contributes to modernizing and improving the quality of education and management in higher education institutions, providing practical and effective solutions for current challenges. The study emphasizes the need to continue investing in staff digital skills development to maximize the benefits of new technologies.

Keywords: Higher education, digitalization, digital economy, educational management, digital transformation.

Introduction. The process of digitalization in the Republic of Moldova has seen multiple attempts at reform and modernization over the past decades. This process began with the implementation of strategies such as "Moldova Electronic" (2005), "Digital Moldova 2020", followed by the "Digital Transformation Strategy of the Republic of Moldova for the years 2023–2030" [1].

The aforementioned strategy envisions the implementation of digital technologies not only to enhance economic indicators but also to improve the quality of services provided to the population, recommending solutions to the private sector and local public administrations. Managing processes without human involvement leads to a significant increase in efficiency and effectiveness of work.

Thus, recent digital transformation directly targets educational institutions in Moldova. In particular, we identify new technologies involved in organizing, managing, and maintaining internal and external regulatory documents of higher education institutions, contributing to the development of this field by reducing paperwork and ensuring transparency [2].

The research aims to analyze and optimize the management of digitalization in the information system of university subdivisions, considering its impact on the efficiency of educational and administrative processes. The objectives of the research are:

1. Evaluate the current status of digitalization in university subdivisions, identifying strengths and vulnerabilities.
2. Analyze the impact of digitalization on educational and research activities, including administrative process efficiency.

3. Identify best practices in implementing digital solutions, including the development of the Electronic Individual Plan and the Departmental E-report.

4. Promote collaboration and transparency in educational and administrative activities through the efficient use of information technologies.

Literature review. The term "digitalization" emerged with the advent of early computers and refers to the process of transforming content from analog to digital format [3]. In a simple economy, physical goods are the primary resource, whereas in a digital economy, information becomes the raw material processed and utilized for effective management solutions.

In specialized literature, this field remains underutilized, yet the issue of document management is pertinent to any system, both theoretically and practically. Existing standard automation solutions and some document management software platforms offer several advantages over traditional workflows reliant on physical media (paper, transparencies, etc.):

- Simplifies the process of direction, drafting, processing, and approval of documents.

- Eliminates document duplication.

- Centralizes document storage.

- Provides instant notification of document status and changes made.

- Easily monitors document completion, coordination, and review timelines.

This approach can be applied across documents of various categories and implemented in any informational flow within higher education institutions. Economically speaking, besides the enumerated advantages, the digitalization process also yields benefits such as savings in paper, storage space, work time, and

increased speed in organizing and processing documents and correspondence [4].

The scientific novelty of this study lies in its in-depth exploration of the theoretical and methodological framework of managing digitalization within university subdivisions' information systems. It involves analyzing how digitalization influences document organization and management, the efficiency of educational and administrative processes, and human resource development. The study identifies key determinants that enhance the effectiveness of this management and evaluates the impact of digitalization on the capacity of educational institutions to adapt and perform in a competitive environment. It thus highlights the benefits and challenges associated with implementing digital solutions at an institutional level.

Methodology. The synthesis of the methodology and research methods outlines the structure and approach used to achieve the formulated goals and objectives. The research was conducted in several essential stages. The first stage involved a detailed analysis of relevant scientific literature on the management of digitalization in the information systems of university subdivisions. The second stage consisted of examining internal regulations to gain a clear picture of the current situation within these subdivisions. The final stage included data processing, validation of research hypotheses, and formulation of recommendations for improving the studied field.

For each stage of the research, various investigation methods were applied, taking into account the specific nature of the study. General research methods included induction and deduction, documentary method, and analytical method. Additionally, specific methods from the economic domain such as observation, case study, experiment, and document analysis were employed to ensure a comprehensive and rigorous approach.

Results.

The digitalization of operational management within university subdivisions.

The proposed research aims to address two challenges faced by university subdivisions:

- a) Digitization of documents at the level of university subdivisions;
- b) Streamlining of work time and material resources.

This study seeks to detail the development process of the Individual Electronic Plan and the Electronic Report tracking teaching, methodological, and scientific activities. Regulatory acts defining the general approaches adopted in the project include [5]:

- Regulation on the standardization of scientific-teaching activities at UTM.
- Framework regulation on the standardization of scientific-teaching activities in higher education.
- Regulation on the use of information systems within UTM.

From our perspective, the key feature of digital transformation lies in qualitative changes in management processes, primarily through the professional application of available software on any computer. New technological solutions require additional investments

in developing employee skills to learn data work culture and digital solutions. These investments directly influence labor productivity and simplify it.

In the initiation and conception phase of digitizing documentation in the university information system, a detailed analysis of the current situation is performed, identifying user needs and expectations, and clearly defining the project's purpose and objectives. Additionally, an analysis of institutional manager needs and expectations is performed using methods such as interviews, surveys, and case studies.

Within the teaching process, there are tasks that need to be allocated to the staff and later collected. These data are processed and subjected to control. However, this manually performed management activity can take several weeks. Digitizing this process can bring significant improvements in terms of the quality of reporting of teaching activities and can lead to the efficient manual process.

Thus, digitizing the teaching process will allow the replacement of traditional methods of data collection and analysis with computer techniques, which will simplify and accelerate the reporting and monitoring of teaching activities. These will include using data management and process automation tools, which will improve efficiency and transparency in data collection and analysis.

Additionally, digitization will contribute to reducing the time and costs associated with the manual reporting process, and the data will be available in real-time, allowing university staff to make timely decisions. Additionally, the performance assessment process will become much simpler and more accurate, thus improving the quality of reporting and ensuring a fair and transparent work method for all university staff.

Digitizing the teaching process is highly important for universities, as it can significantly improve the efficiency and transparency of internal processes, thereby enhancing the quality of teaching, methodological, and scientific activities of the institution.

In the context of the established goals of digitizing documentation within the university information system, the use of the Excel application within the MS Office universal package, especially the Business Intelligence (BI) module, is proposed as the primary tool. The BI solution consists of a set of applications and technologies designed to collect, store, analyze, share, and provide access to data, enabling managers to make efficient decisions regardless of their hierarchical position. Once implemented, BI solutions allow the transition from management based on past events to efficient management, where decisions are based on forecasts and predictions about the operating environment. Thus, institutional managers can make decisions based on concrete and real-time data, leading to more efficient management and improved quality of the teaching process.

Furthermore, the use of BI solutions can lead to increased institution performance by quickly identifying problems and errors in the teaching process and quickly adapting it to user needs and expectations.

According to the established objectives, two Excel files have been developed:

The Individual Plan (E-Plan) is a document completed by each teaching staff member at the end of the academic year and includes four sections, with all activities being scored and regulated [6]:

1. Teaching norm/task (SD) refers to the framework of rules and standards that regulate teaching activities in education [6]. This includes:

- Classroom teaching activities;
- Non-classroom teaching activities.

In accordance with the established teaching norm to streamline calculations and time management, and considering the regulations regarding the normative framework of scientific and teaching activities at the Technical University of Moldova, the use of an Excel form integrating these components is proposed. This tool will facilitate the organization, monitoring, and evaluation of teaching activities, thereby optimizing the educational process and improving time resource management (Fig. 1).

Teaching Load																
Fall Semester																
Course/Module Name According to Curriculum Plan	Form of Study	Series / Group	No. of Students	Lecture Activity					Non-Lecture Activity							
				Lectures	Practical Work/Seminars	Laboratory Work	Exam Consultations	Supervision of Instructional Practice Stages	Total Auditory Hours	Supervision of Production Practice Stages	Projects/Year	Professors' Guidance of Students' Individual	Current Consultations	Evaluations:		Total Non-Auditory Hours
											Current (Assessments)	Final (Exams)	Assistance at Exams			
Bachelor's Degree									0,00						0,00	0,00
									0,00						0,00	0,00
									0,00						0,00	0,00
									0,00						0,00	0,00
									0,00						0,00	0,00
Master's Degree				0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
									0,00						0,00	0,00
									0,00						0,00	0,00
									0,00						0,00	0,00
									0,00						0,00	0,00
									0,00						0,00	0,00
					0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00

Fig. 1. Teaching Task Spreadsheet

Source: developed by the authors based on reference [6]

2. Methodological Activity/Task (SM) refers to the set of activities and processes through which teaching staff prepare and organize their teaching efforts, aiming to optimize student learning. This activity is essential for ensuring the quality of education and developing the necessary skills for students.

Methodological activities have been integrated into the Individual Plan, detailing staffing and scheduling, with the aim of continuously monitoring their implementation (Fig. 2).

Methodical Task						
			Planned		Completed	
II.1. Development of a curriculum plan			number of plans	number of authors	hours	hours
Plan Name 1					0,00	0,00
Plan Name 2					0,00	0,00
II.2. "Preparation for courses, seminars, laboratories (Professors, Associate Professors - 100 hours; Lecturers - 150 hours; Assistant Professors - 200 hours in total per			hours		hours	hours
Name 1					0,00	0,00
Name 2						

Fig. 2. Methodological Task Spreadsheet

Source: developed by the authors based on reference [9]

This approach allows for systematic evaluation of progress in implementing teaching strategies, thereby ensuring continuous improvement in the quality of the

educational process and efficient adaptation to students' needs.

3. Research Activity/Scientific Task (RA/ST) refers to the systematic process of exploring and investi-

gating scientific or technical problems, aimed at generating new knowledge or developing innovative solutions (Fig. 3).

Scientific task							
		Planned			Completed		
III.1. Books, monographs, chapters in joint monographs, specialized treaties published by foreign publishers (with ISBN)		author's papers	number of authors	hours	author's papers	number of authors	hours
6	Name 1			0,00			0,00
7	Name 2			0,00			0,00
8	Name 3			0,00			0,00
9	Name 4			0,00			0,00
10	Name 5			0,00			0,00
11							
III.2. Cărți, monografii, capitole în monografii comune, tratate de specialitate publicate la edituri naționale recunoscute (cu ISBN)		author's papers	number of authors	hours	author's papers	number of authors	hours
13	Name 1			0,00			0,00

Fig. 3. Spreadsheet "Scientific Task"

Source: Developed by the authors based on reference [6]

Scientific activity has been digitized according to the figure above with the aim of facilitating rapid and efficient access to information, improving collaboration among researchers, and ensuring better resource management. Additionally, the digital format enhances transparency and facilitates monitoring of scientific activities, thereby supporting innovation and progress in the field of study.

4. Community or ancillary activity (CA) of an academic staff refers to their involvement in activities and initiatives that support education and community development outside formal teaching hours. These activities aim to strengthen the bond between the educational institution and the community, promoting a more integrated educational environment and supporting the personal and professional development of students (Fig. 4).

Community task					
		Planned		Completed	
IV.1. Activity in expert committees		number of committees	hours	number of committees	hours
7	Internaționale		0,00		0,00
8	Naționale		0,00		0,00
9					
IV.2. Activity in specialized committees (Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Education, World Bank, etc.		number of committees	hours	number of committees	hours
11	Internaționale		0,00		0,00

Fig. 4. Excel File for Automating the "Community Task" Page

Source: Developed by the authors based on reference [6]

Based on the analyzed information, the performance indicator will be determined using the digitized Individual Plan. This approach will enable a systematic and objective evaluation of the activities carried out, facilitating progress monitoring and identifying areas that need improvement. Thus, the performance indicator will contribute to optimizing the educational process and supporting the continuous professional development of teaching staff, according to Formula (1):

$$K = TL*0,25+MT*0,3+ST*0,3+CT*0,15 \quad (1)$$

The accumulated score of the teaching staff will be automatically determined by the program and classified as: unsatisfactory, satisfactory, good, or excellent (see Table 1).

Table 1.

Academic rank	Score assigned for rating			
	Unsatisfactory	Satisfactory	Good	Excellent
Full professor	<650	<750	<950	>950
Associate professor	<550	<650	<850	>850
Lecturer	<500	<600	<750	>750
Assistant professor.	<450	<550	<700	>700

Source: Authors' elaboration based on reference [9]

Based on the established criteria, both the subdivision manager and each teaching staff member individually will be able to determine the rating for their activities. This evaluation will be based on established performance indicators, ensuring an objective and fair

assessment of each teacher's contribution to the educational process. This approach will support transparency and continuous improvement of teaching activities (Fig. 5).

INDIVIDUAL PLAN of academic staff for the 2024-2025 year

SELF-EVALUATION SHEET of Mr./Ms.

position: **associate professor**

scientific title: **Ph.D.**

Teaching position (select from the dropdown list): **associate professor**

Teaching Load: **0,00**

	Planned	Completed
Teaching Load	0,00	0,00
Methodical Task	0,00	0,00
Scientific Task	0,00	0,00
Community Task	0,00	0,00

FINAL SCORE

Assessment: **0,00**

Fig. 5. Spreadsheet for Assessing Ratings in "E-Individual Plan"

Source: developed by the authors

At the same time, each teaching staff member will be able to identify vulnerable areas in their own activities and focus efforts on addressing them. This awareness facilitates continuous improvement of individual performance and promotes professional development, thereby enhancing the quality of the educational process.

The departmental electronic report, managed as an Excel file in the department's cloud space, will be completed by teaching staff. This reporting structure facilitates quick access and efficient data organization, enabling coherent performance analysis and supporting decision-making within the department.

The developed electronic report allows separate centralization of information for undergraduate (Bachelor's) and graduate (Master's) cycles using the Power Query module in Excel. This structure enables distinct evaluation of academic performances in each study cycle, thereby contributing to more efficient management and pinpointing specific areas for improvement at each stage of the educational process.

Following the implementation of the digitalization project in the university information system, the following significant outcomes can be achieved:

- Departmental staff will benefit from skill enhancement through the training program.
- Self-assessment of professional performances of teaching staff will be facilitated through the obtained rating.
- Reference materials collected for beneficiaries can be subsequently replicated and distributed upon request to other interested subdivisions.
- The database will be utilized for statistical purposes, contributing to the improvement and streamlining of analysis and reporting activities.

Conclusions. The implementation of digital technologies represents an efficient approach to achieving ambitious national objectives. Systems enriched with

greater volumes of information can conduct more precise analyses and anticipate materializing risks, thereby enhancing our performance and ensuring process transparency.

The research conducted and the practical applicability of the product obtained, namely the Individual Plan and the Departmental E-report, have achieved their intended purpose and will contribute to improving the quality of education, optimizing the teaching process, and fostering continuous professional development of teaching staff. These tools will also support rapid adaptation to changes in the educational environment and promote a culture of excellence in education:

- The implementation of the Electronic Individual Plan facilitates systematic monitoring of teaching activities, allowing teachers to track their progress and continuously improve their performance.
- The Departmental E-report enables separate centralization of data for the Bachelor's (cycle I) and Master's (cycle II) programs, providing a solid foundation for evaluating and comparing academic performances in each study cycle.
- The accessibility and efficient organization of information support decision-making at the subdivision level, contributing to the formulation of educational strategies better suited to students' needs.
- The digitalization of these processes promotes transparency in teaching activities and encourages collaboration among teaching staff, facilitating the exchange of best practices and educational resources.

References

1. Concept. Strategia de transformare digitală a Republicii Moldova pentru anii 2023–2030 (STDM 2030) [online]. Available: <https://egov.md/ro/node/39487>
2. KHAMDAMOV U.R., ABDULLAEV A.I., ELOV J.B.. Conceptual Model of the Education Management Information System for Higher Education

Institutions [online]. In: International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering. Volume 9, No.5, September – October 2020. India. –p.7295- 7300. Available: <https://www.warse.org/IJATCSE/static/pdf/file/ijatcse59952020.pdf>

3. BLOOMBERG J. (2018, April 29). Digitization, digitalization, and digital transformation: confuse them at your Peril. Forbes. Available: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/jasonbloomberg/2018/04/29/digitization-digitalization-and-digital-transformation-confuse-them-at-your-peril/?sh=44691a252f2c>

4. TÎRȘU V. Instrumente Microsoft de business intelligence – soluție pentru inteligența afacerii

[online]. În: Materialele Conferinței Științifice Internaționale „Paradigme moderne în dezvoltarea economiei naționale și mondiale”, 1-2 noiembrie 2019. Chișinău: CEP USM., p.520-528. ISBN 978-9975-149-73-0. Available:

https://ibn.idsi.md/ro/vizualizare_articol/100532/gscholar

5. Acte normative UTM. Available: <https://utm.md/administratia/acte-normative/>

6. Regulament cu privire la normarea activității științifico-didactice în UTM. Available: <https://utm.md/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/regulament-normare-21.05.2024.pdf>